

Effect of associated cation on the exchange of $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ in acetone-water media, using strongly basic anion exchanger Amberlite IRA-400 in nitrate form

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Abstract : The effect of associated cation on the exchange of univalent ions in acetone-water media; $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ system was studied with one g of resin using Amberlite IRA-400 (20–40 mesh) in nitrate form. The chloride exchange increased in all the cases with increase in acetone percentage of the solutions. But, the extent of exchange in different cases was different when different salts were used.

Keywords : Ion-exchanger, mixed solvents, metal ions.

The selectivity of an ion for resin phase is influenced by the variation of the ionic composition of the exchanger (i.e. X_{B_R}). In mixed solvents, the solvent composition is also an important factor and influences the activities of counter ions present in the exchange system. The availability of a certain number of ions in the solution not only depends on the nature of the solvent, but also on the nature of the compound used. Solvent can also influence their solvation tendencies¹. The present study reports on the exchange of an anion associated with different types of cations.

Experimental

To see the effect of associated cation on the exchange of univalent anions in acetone-water media $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ system was studied with one g of the resin. Amberlite IRA-400 (20–40 mesh) in nitrate form in 0, 10, 20, 40, 60% of aqueous acetone (v/v) solutions. The chlorides of lithium, sodium, potassium and ammonium (B.D.H.) were used for the experiment. Stock solutions were prepared in deionised water to give 0–1 M solutions. Exchange capacity was determined 4.5 meq/g of the air dried resin.

Selectivity studies were carried out by batch technique (50 ml) at room temperature for equilibrium studies. A time period of about 24 h was allowed to attain the equilibrium. The anion concentration after exchange were obtained by titrating aliquots (5 mL) from these batches. Selectivity coefficients (K_a) values were calculated as

$$K_a = \frac{X_{B_R} \cdot C_{A_w}}{X_{A_R} \cdot C_{B_w}}$$

Results and discussion

The chloride exchange increased in all the cases with increase in acetone percentages of the solutions. The extent of exchange (Table 1) shows the order as : $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{NH}_4^+$. That nature of the associated cation influences the exchange of an anion (in the present case a Cl^- ion) (Table 2). Attempts have been made to find some reasoning of this and, therefore, the observed K_a values have been plotted against effective hydrated cationic sizes of associated cation in each of the different solvent systems. The relevant data are given in Table 2 and the trend is shown in Fig. 1.

When the effect of associated cation on the exchange of an anion was studied by using lithium, sodium, potassium and ammonium chlorides for bringing about $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ exchange on strong-base exchanger, the selectivity coefficients values ($K_{a_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{Cl}}}$) were found to be different in the four cases (Table 1). Unexpectedly use of lithium chloride gave higher K_a values for $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ exchange than with NaCl , KCl and NH_4Cl at all acetone concentrations. This can be interpreted in terms of the polarisability of an anion in solution. This polarisability is influenced by the associated cation also. The cations in solution are all hydrated and their sizes in solution increase with decreasing radii (Table 2). Thus lithium ion in solution has largest hydrated ionic size. Associated chloride ion in the vicinity of such an ion in solution will be less polarized as compared to ions, which have smaller hydrated ionic sizes. The polarisability of exchanging chloride ion will be expected to be influenced more by K^+ than by Na^+ or Li^+ , while NH_4^+ will be less than K^+ . The observed

Table 1. Exchange of Cl^- ion associated with different cations

Sl. no.	Acetone % (v/v)	K_a for $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ exchange			
		Li^+	Na^+	K^+	NH_4^+
1.	0	0.3038	0.2028	0.2028	0.1427
2.	10	0.3149	0.2108	0.2117	0.1832
3.	20	0.3268	0.2194	0.2151	0.1950
4.	40	0.4139	0.2819	0.2764	0.2511
5.	60	0.6510	0.4440	0.4364	0.3913

Table 2. Radii of associated cations

Sl. no.	Associated cation in anion-exchange	Cationic radii in Å	
		Hydrated	Naked
1.	Li^+	10.00	0.68
2.	Na^+	7.90	0.98
3.	K^+	5.30	1.33
4.	NH_4^+	5.37	1.43

trend (Fig. 1) appears to be the result of interaction involving associated cation-water in a more emphatic manner than anion-water.

Fig. 1. Effect of associated cation size in the exchange of Cl^- against NO_3^- in acetone-water media.

We can also consider the observed effect of the changing cation size of the chloride salts used in exchange studies in a different way using the concept of water structure enforced effects. The effect of ions present in water or dissolved in water on its structure has been analyzed². These ions create a sort of disorder in the water structure so that the measured entropy changes in the solutions of ions in water can be co-related to this disorder. Thus, ΔS° values in cal/deg/mole of Li^+ (-39.6), Na^+ (-33.9), K^+ (-25.3) and also of anions as F^- (-40.9), Cl^- (-26.6), Br^- (-22.7) and I^- (-18.5) could be related to this disorder by calculating standard entropy loss per mole for a salt and comparing it with that for 2 g atoms of argon. Thus, for KCl the net entropy loss per mole will be $25.3 + 26.6 = 51.9$, while it is $2 \times 30.2 = 60.4$ for 2 g atoms of argon. Such a comparison shows that there is a reduction in entropy loss for KCl of about 8.1 units (This ion goes on decreasing with smaller size of the cation). This is explained as the net effect of the ionic charges of K^+ and Cl^- ions. This effect appears in spite of the fact that in the immediate vicinity of the ion there is a layer of firmly oriented water molecules (called as frozen condition). The formation of this layer gives rise to an entropy loss of about 12 cal/deg/mole. Other sources of entropy loss increase an amount (~ 20 cal/deg/mole) due to the reduction of free volume when the (gas) ion enters the solution and also a contribution due to the partial orientation of water molecules in layers beyond the first, when these three losses are subtracted from the entropy values of mono atomic ions in solution, they give the values for structure breaking entropy of the ion. For all alkali metal ions structure breaking entropy term corresponds to a considerable increase in disorder. Thus, if LiCl, NaCl and KCl are separately added to an aqueous solution there will be a greater disorder in the system when a larger cation is present in the solution with a chloride ion. In other words, water structure will be more disrupted. The halides in a general way go into the resin phase as they find more disorderly structured water in

resin : while water outside is more orderly. The less hydrated halides ion do not prefer the aqueous phase and the water-structure enforced ion-pairing leads to their exchange on the resin.

Now with change of cation type, the orderly behavior of the outside water is disturbed. It is more for K^+ , less for Na^+ and least for Li^+ , hence the associated chloride ion finds its place into the resin phase more due to water-structure enforced ion-pairing when Li^+ ion is present with it and which does not create disorder in the water-structure (its ΔS° for this being -1.1 cal/deg/mole). The process will become reversed when the outside solution is less structured, the anion will now have no need to search for a more disturbed structure of water in the resin phase. This type of condition prevails in solution also hence, there is no pushing of chloride ion to that much extent when Na^+ or K^+ are present together with chloride as the electrolyte in outside solution.

The reasoning which depends on the effect of water-structure on exchanges of anions, can very well account

of the observed trends of chloride exchange against NO_3^- .

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